

PERSONALITY TRAITS OF COLLEGE STUDENTS IN WORLD CITI COLLEGES QUEZON CITY

Sharmaine A. Agana, Giulia Zaldric Espartero, Yuki Jarka S. Lacdao,
Winella Alohdia F. Rodriguez, Joselito F. Andez

Department of Psychology, World Citi Colleges, Quezon City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Personality traits are characteristics that describe an individual's behavior. These traits help shape our lived experiences as we progress through life. One of the most significant milestones of an individual is entering college, earning a degree, meeting new people, and embracing a new environment. Taking this into account, the study aims to investigate the personality traits of extraversion, loneliness, and belongingness among college students. Extraversion is a trait marked by outgoingness and energy. Loneliness is the feeling of isolation, which creates a gap in experiences as an individual socializes. Belongingness is the feeling of connection to a group, marked by a sense of community on campus. A descriptive-quantitative research design will be used to approach the research objectives. A survey questionnaire will be used as the instrument for collecting the data needed for this study. The questionnaires were adopted, and ANOVA and Pearson's R correlation were utilized to interpret the results. The respondents for this study will come from the 11 programs at World Citi Colleges, Quezon City Campus. Using proportionate random sampling, 336 individuals will be surveyed for this research. The study will contribute to the body of knowledge regarding loneliness and belongingness, offering insights that can help improve students' campus experiences.

Keywords: *Personality Traits, Student Classification, Loneliness, Extraversion, Belongingness*

INTRODUCTION

College plays a significant role in an individual's life, offering opportunities for higher education and exposure to a diverse range of people. However, certain factors, such as a sense of belonging and feelings of loneliness, may impact on these opportunities. Universities are filled with diverse individuals and communities, and while some students may find it easy to feel a sense of belonging within a group, others may face challenges in doing so.

A key component of college success is developing a sense of belonging—whether among peers, in the classroom, or within the campus community. Transfer students represent a diverse and growing population that has often been overlooked in both academic literature and at higher education institutions in the United States (Gardner et al., 2021; Sherman, L.E et al., 2013; Harper & Thiry, 2023; Lester, 2013; Tobolowsky & Cox, 2012). During the course of higher education, one-third of college students transfer at least once, and 25% of those who transfer are likely to transfer more than once (Matthews, 2015).

Transferring to a new institution can lead to various behavioral and psychological changes, along with alterations in peer relationships (Wang et al., 2019; Wickersham, 2020). The sudden disruption in a student's routine may gradually impact their motivation to learn, academic performance, and overall attitude toward education (Raza et al., 2020; Tobolowsky & Bers, 2019). Numerous studies have explored the relationship between a lack of belonging and feelings of loneliness among college students (Avci, 2023; Dost & Mazzoli, 2023; Froehlich et al., 2023). Research highlights the interconnectedness of belonging and loneliness (Asghar & Iqbal, 2021; Avci, 2023; Gilchrist, 2023; Matthews et al., 2019; Vytniorgu et al., 2023). However, there remains a gap in understanding non-transfer students, with much of the literature on the topic being outdated (Baumeister & Leary, 2017; Eccles et al., 2023; Hawkey & Cacioppo, 2010). Additionally, studies addressing transfer students' experiences of loneliness and belonging remain limited (Ardissone et al., 2023; Jaud et al., 2023), as do studies incorporating gender as a demographic factor (Bharti, 2021; Correia et al., 2022; Dost & Mazzoli, 2023; Subasi, 2023). This study seeks to address these gaps, particularly by contributing to the limited research conducted after the COVID-19 pandemic (Avci, 2023; Jaud et al., 2023).

Loneliness, as defined by Peplau and Perlman (1981), is characterized by three primary aspects: it is a personal experience, a distressing and upsetting mood, and it results from a lack of human relationships (Ballard, 2019). A recent systematic review further defines loneliness as “social discomfort caused by a perceived deficit in the quantity or quality of an individual's social connections” (Osborn et al., 2020).

Several theories have been proposed to explain the connection between the Big Five and loneliness; behavioral genetic research suggests that, while shared genetic variables significantly contribute to this link, environmental factors also play a role (Schermer & Martin, 2019). Loneliness may be influenced by societal standards regarding social connection, individuals in looser cultures are more likely to live alone, whereas those in tighter cultures may have less freedom in choosing their social circles to form closer

connections (Vo, M.T.H. et al., 2021). Loneliness is a painful universal psychological experience that has serious consequences for college students' mental health and wellbeing (Moeller & Seehuus, 2019; Tanhan, 2020). Loneliness is a universal emotion that most of us experience at least once during our lifetime. When one sees a disconnect between the desires and experiences of social interaction, people are said to be in a condition of loneliness. Being without a certain necessary relationship or combination of relationships, as opposed to being alone, is what causes loneliness. Numerous research found that loneliness had a detrimental effect on psychological adjustment and general well-being (Arslan et al., 2020). There are negative effects of loneliness on both mental and physical health, that recent studies have discovered that loneliness can anticipate future episodes of sadness and anxiety (Jalilian et al., 2023; Lee, 2019; Li et al., 2023).

When COVID-19 came it posed challenges in building relationships among the students due to restrictions and having to communicate through online. It is important to build rapport among students through social cues and nonverbal communication (Song et al., 2019). Which in the case of COVID-19 restricts students from building these things to foster a relationship. Online classes have reduced the opportunity for students to connect deeply and struggle in learning as isolation causes the increase in feelings of loneliness (Hew & Huang, 2023; Lovell & Webber, 2023; Sherblom, 2010). According to Jung et al. (2021), uncertainty is the most significant effect of distance learning during COVID-19, students missing the opportunities to get to know each other. Students having a sense of peer unfamiliarity is said to largely affect the engagement of a student during the whole group session, which causes them to avoid interactions that will make them in front of other students like asking inquiries and debates (Hopwood, 2023).

School loneliness is associated with poor affect and is negatively associated with positive affect and life satisfaction (Twenge et al., 2021). Loneliness, according to studies, is on the rise, particularly among younger generations. The commonly held belief that loneliness primarily affects older people (Vasileiou et al., 2019; Barreto et al., 2022). Loneliness among students has also been linked to students' experiences with housing and, as earlier study has shown, with links (or lack thereof) to the larger community outside of the university (Vytniorgu et al., 2021). In all age groups and across nations, men see loneliness as more stigmatizing and controllable than women (Barreto et al., 2022).

Research indicates that people have a "need to belong," which drives them to look for and keep a certain number of enduring, solid relationships with both people and groups. Even though everyone wants to fit in and be accepted by society, groupings, people's yearning for acceptance and a sense of belonging varies (Brownsword & Sundby, 2019). Belonging is linked to student well-being, academic achievement, and retention. It symbolizes feelings of acceptance and connection. The four realms of academic, social, environmental, and personal space comprise the concept of belonging (Ahn & Dais, 2019).

According to Hou and Chumeng (2023), individuals that scored high in loneliness are lacking social needs and lacking information from their social environment. Which makes

them fear not being able to build interpersonal relationships and missing information. This shows the consequences of being socially isolated from each other due to COVID-19 restrictions. Belongingness has been hard during the time of COVID as this is one of the large fatalities of the pandemic. Having technology as our means of belonging during the remote times, as belonging in social groups during that time brings out worry of virus transmission rather than a helping hand to attain belongingness (Andreadis & Marshall, 2023).

Despite the fact that school belonging has been studied for many years, university students' feeling of belonging has been severely underestimated since the epidemic. Individuals' sense of belonging to a particular institution, environment, social activity, and culture contributes to well-being in a variety of ways, including intellectual, occupational, psychological, and physical (Arslan & Coşkun, 2023; Haim-Litevsky et al., 2023). Students with a low feeling of belonging have been linked to social anxiety, loneliness, discomfort, and suicide ideation (Arslan, 2019, 2020; Arslan & Coskun, 2023; Moeller et al., 2020). According to Arnett (2006), emerging people gain their identity through social interactions, and this phase overlaps with university years. Developing and deepening relationships throughout university years, on the other hand, is underpinned by belongingness, which supports a high level of well-being (Arslan, 2020, 2021; Lambert et al., 2013). A strong sense of belonging improves quality of life, satisfaction, academic performance, and motivation, which protects people from potential psychological disorders (Arslan, 2021).

An interview in 2022 about how the need to belong drives human behavior, Geoffrey Cohen, PhD, mentioned that human nature includes the need for belonging, which is rather necessary. When someone feels uncomfortable or that their feeling of belonging is under jeopardy, it can have a profound impact on them; in fact, this could cause discomfort and self-doubt (Cohen, 2022). A person's ability to connect with others is crucial since it will enable the person to overcome the possibility of feeling uncomfortable in unfamiliar surroundings. In light of this, a transfer student will understandably feel alienated from their new classmates since they can immediately tell that they have established a group (Cohen, 2022). Nonetheless, it is also understandable that the transferees would want a sense of belonging as they want to avoid the awkward situations they are encountering with their new classmates, and they want to stay up to date. According to Suryadi (2023), being appreciated, accepted, and included in school is a complex concept that connects the behavioral and emotional elements.

Belongingness can also provide emotional support to students who are dealing with unpleasant circumstances, such as the death of a loved one (McNally et al., 2021). As a result, belonging in college is vital for both academic success and psychological well-being (Arslan, 2021). Greater college belongingness also connects favorably with life satisfaction for first-generation college students (Duffy et al., 2020).

According to (Walton, 2021), the majority of these experiments utilize the social belonging intervention, a brief reading and writing exercise designed to alleviate students' concerns about belonging. This intervention explains everyday issues related to the transition to

college, such as receiving critical feedback on schoolwork, and emphasizes that these challenges are common and typically diminish over time. Furthermore, belonging uncertainty also emerges as social withdrawal, reaching to the extent that is intimately related to leaving a particular setting, such as the university. This implies that confusion about belonging may encourage the intention to drop out of higher education according to (Hohne & Zander 2019), given the significance of dropout intentions as facilitators of decision-making (Bäulke et al., 2021), it stands to reason that uncertainty about belonging may lead to actual dropout.

A study conducted by Kural and Ozyurt (2021) in which they have been consistently shown that personality and perceived stress, on their own, are critical components of university transition for college students. There is little understanding about the connection between personality and perceived stress, and the students' adjustment towards the university.

One of the main characteristics of the five-factor model (FFM) is extraversion, which has been highlighted as a higher-order factor in nearly all taxonomy schemes of personality that have been created. One of the most important aspects of the study of personality for a long time has been extraversion vs introversion. Extraverted individuals are thought of as extroverts, whilst introverts are thought of as having low levels of extraversion. There are numerous ways in which extraversion can account for the covariation of behaviors, a key area of study in the realm of personality. More precisely, it has been found that extraversion is an individual different characteristic that influences a wide range of employee behaviors (Brownsword. & Sundby, 2019).

According to Audet et al. (2021), extraversion, characterized by an outgoing personality and a need for social engagement, can significantly impact a college student's experience. Extraversion, sometimes known as surgency, is characterized by assertiveness, energy, and gregarious behaviors (Grice, 2019). It indicates how much stimulation and social engagement a person enjoys. For instance, consider someone with a high extraversion score on a personality test—they enjoy socializing. Given the positive nature of extraverts, it may be improbable and reported that they feel dread, wrath, or other negative emotions (Agbaria and Mokh; Nikčević et al., 2021)

Research Questions

This study investigated the personality traits of the college students in World Citi Colleges. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex; and
 - 1.3 Student Classification?

2. What is the level of personality traits of college students according to:
 - 2.1 Extraversion;
 - 2.2 Loneliness; and
 - 2.3 Belongingness?
3. Is there a significant difference among the personality traits of college students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the personality traits and profile of the respondents?
5. What recommendations can be proposed to enhance personality traits based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers conducted a Descriptive-Quantitative study to gather knowledge and information on the topic, "Navigating the Campus Experience: Extraversion as a Moderator of Student Classification, Loneliness, and Belongingness among World Citi Colleges QC Students." As students of BS in Psychology, the researchers focused on Transferee and Non-Transferee students to understand the relationship between their levels of belongingness and loneliness, as well as how extraversion moderates these factors.

In this study, the researchers utilized questionnaires to collect data and examine the moderating effects among the variables. ANCOVA was used to test the relationship between the two variables—levels of belongingness and loneliness—across different student classifications. A T-Test was also employed to determine the significance of the relationship between these variables.

The researchers administered an efficient online survey questionnaire to gather responses from the participants. This approach enabled the examination of the moderating role of extraversion and the measurement of levels of loneliness and belongingness. Online surveys were used to collect and analyze responses in order to achieve the study's objectives.

By conducting the tests mentioned above, the researchers were able to address the primary research questions. After gathering data from participants, conclusions were drawn based on the findings, leading to an understanding of the relationship between student classification and the levels of belongingness and loneliness.

The research was conducted at World Citi Colleges, Inc., Quezon City Campus. The department where the study took place encompassed the entire course, with 336 respondents selected for the study. The study was conducted during the school year 2023–2024. World Citi Colleges, Inc., Quezon City, was chosen as the research locale because the researchers believed that the educational institution offered a large population, which would provide valid and reliable data for the study. The sizable population at World Citi Colleges was considered essential for this study.

The respondents of the study were the students at World Citi Colleges, Quezon City, from all programs and year levels. The total number of respondents was 359, representing the various programs offered at World Citi Colleges QC. They were categorized as old or new students based on the distributed survey questionnaires

The research instrument used to collect the data for this study was a survey form administered via Google Forms. The study also utilized adopted open-access questionnaires for each variable, namely the UCLA Loneliness Scale (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.94), the Levett-Jones Belongingness Scale (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.92), and the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.70-0.90). To ensure the safety and confidentiality of the responses, the researchers also prepared an informed consent form and a letter for the respondents. These instruments were used to collect efficient and reliable data.

For this study, the risks posed to the human subjects were minimal, including potential disruption of class hours and minor psychological distress due to self-assessment. To safeguard the respondents' basic rights, the right to self-determination was observed by providing complete information about the study before securing informed consent to participate. The study also credited the authors of the questionnaires used by acknowledging their contributions to the creation of the instruments. The questionnaires, which were openly accessible on the internet, could potentially be subject to misuse. Considering these circumstances, the researchers ensured that proper safekeeping of the documents was implemented to respect the participants' right to confidentiality, as well as the authors' right to be credited for their work.

The procedures that the researchers followed to gather the data needed for the study. First, the researchers prepared a consent form to obtain the participants' permission to participate in the survey. Second, after obtaining their consent, the researchers provided the participants with the link to the Google survey form. Third, once the participants completed the forms and the target number of respondents was reached, the researchers collected the data from the forms and organized it based on the variables.

The data gathered were arranged in tabulated form and computed manually with the aid of computer software to accurately determine the interpretation of the results. The data gathered were arranged in tabulated form and computed manually with the aid of computer software to accurately determine the interpretation of the results. ANOVA which is a statistical tool used to compare the means of three or more groups to determine statistically significant difference among them. In this study, it is used to determine the significant difference among the personality traits of college students such as loneliness, extraversion, and belongingness. This study applied Two-Factor without replication to compare mean scores across groups. T-test was used to determine the significant differences among the personality traits of the college students. It specifically compared the levels of extraversion, loneliness, and belongingness and applied paired two-sample T-test that is useful in comparing two related groups to see if their means differ significantly. This statistical tool provided additional validation to the statistical tool ANOVA and concluding the significant difference among the personality traits. Pearson's R correlation is used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship among two

continuous variables. In this study, this statistical tool was used to determine the relationship among students' personality traits such as extraversion, loneliness, and belongingness and the demographic profile such as age, sex, and student classification. This tool helped in understanding the negative and positive influence among the personality traits and the academic setting. Weighted Mean was used in Profiles of the respondents, Level of Personality Traits according to Loneliness and Level of Personality Traits according to Belongingness where personality traits such as extraversion, loneliness, and sense of belonging were evaluated. Showing some students were neutral on extraversion but leaned toward introverted actions. Loneliness varied, with some students feeling occasionally lonely, while others felt socially connected.

The feeling of belongingness was scored high on average indicating that students tend to feel accepted and incorporated into their college community. Simple Percentage, along with the participants' ages, gender, and student class level. This facilitated the researchers in understanding the sample better. This technique summarizes information about respondents' profiles by computing the percentage on each response so that the relative size of a particular group can be determined against the entire sample. This is useful for identifying the most important issue in the comparison of different figures. Implicit frequency in categorization also aided in representation of respondent characteristics such that the responses given by the participants in the different demographic categories were made clear. This approach records the number of times a particular response or category occurs in the data set and shows the summary of data by frequency of unique values.

RESULTS

In this chapter, the researchers will present the results of the data gathering, incorporating the findings to address the research objectives and highlighting the significant results.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Demographic Profile	Categories	f	%
Age	18	3	0.84%
	19	38	10.58%
	20	89	24.79%
	21	86	23.96%

	22	78	21.73%
	23	46	12.81%
	24	12	3.34%
	25	2	0.56%
	28	2	0.56%
	30	2	0.56%
	41	1	0.28%
Total		359	100.00%
Sex	Female	217	60.45%
	Male	142	39.55%
Total		359	100.00%
Student Classification	Old Student	289	80.50%
	New Student	70	19.50%
Total		359	100.00%

Table 1 shows the results of a profile of respondents, the age distribution of responses shows that the majority are 20 years old, which makes up (24.79%) of the sample. This is closely followed by 21- and 22-year-olds, who contribute (23.96%) and (21.73%), respectively. (10.58%) of respondents are aged 19 or younger. Other age groups, such as those aged 18, 23, 24, 25, 28, 30, and 41, each make up for less than (13%) of the sample, with the smallest groups ages 25, 28, 30, and 41 contributing less than (1%) each. In terms of gender distribution, the sample is largely female, with women contributing (60.45%) of respondents and men contributing (39.55%). In terms of student

classification, most respondents are classified as old students (80.50%), while new students represent (19.50%) of the total. In summary, the respondent profile is characterized by a predominance of females, the majority of respondents are aged 19 to 22, and a large number of older students.

Table 2
Level of Personality Traits according to Extraversion

Extraversion	Weighted mean	Standard deviation	Interpretation
1. Don't talk a lot.	3.075209	1.204008	Neutral
2. Keep in the background	3.32312	1.052422	Neutral
3. Have little to say	2.994429	1.179419	Neutral
4. Don't like to draw attention to myself.	3.426184	1.145545	Neutral
5. I am quiet around strangers.	3.604457	1.261631	Slightly Agree
6. I am the life of the party.	2.972067	1.373744	Neutral
7. Feel comfortable around people.	3.629526	1.064573	Slightly Agree
8. Start conversations.	3.554318	1.131927	Slightly agree
9. Talk to a lot of different people at parties.	3.287709	1.27172	Neutral
10. Don't mind being the center of attention.	3.097493	1.313433	Neutral

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Strongly Agree, 3.41-4.20 Agree, 2.61-3.40 Neutral, 1.81-2.60 Disagree, 1.00-1.80 Strongly Disagree

This study investigated the level of extraversion among college students at World Citi Colleges by using a series of statements. According to table 2, many students showed no opinion regarding most extraversion traits. For example, phrases like “Don't talk a lot” (M: 3.08, SD: 1.20), “Keep in the background” (M: 3.32, SD: 1.05), and “Have little to say” (M: 2.99, SD: 1.18) meant that learners neither strongly agreed nor disagreed with these qualities ascribed to them. Neutral responses were also observed for “I am the life of the party” (M: 2.97, SD: 1.37) and “Talk to a lot of different people at parties” (Mean: 3.29, SD: 1.27). However there was a slight concurrence among pupils with such statements as “Don't like to draw attention to myself” (M=3.43, SD =1.14), “I am quiet around strangers” (Mean=3.60, SD=1.26), “Feel comfortable around people” (M=3.63, SD=1.06), and “Start conversations” (Mode=3.55, SD=1.13); this implies a bias toward being more introverted and less extroverted in social contexts for those who slightly endorsed that view point across all cases used in this experiment.

Table 3 shows that among the students examined, this study also analyzed the extent of loneliness. The answers varied, meaning diverse experiences of loneliness. Such as “I lack companionship” (M: 2.45, SD: 0.88) or “There is no one I can turn to” (M: 2.28, SD: 0.94), which means that isolation is not normally felt by students frequently. On the other hand, expressions like “I feel part of a group of friends,” (M: 3.27, SD: 0.88), “I have a lot in common with people around me,” (M: 3.05, SD: 0.78), and “There are people who really

understand me” (M: 3.21, SD: .82) showed that sometimes students had a sense of belonging and understanding within their social circles. For instance, those mixed responses can be understood as some student feeling connected while others experience occasional periods of loneliness.

Table 3
Level of Personality Traits according to Loneliness

Loneliness	Mean	SD	Interpretation
2. I lack companionship.	2.454286	0.884066	Rarely
3. There is no one I can turn to.	2.284123	0.941026	Rarely
5. I feel part of a group of friends.	3.272981	0.88002	Sometimes
6. I have a lot in common with the people around me.	3.047619	0.775667	Sometimes
9. I am an outgoing person.	2.849582	0.97436	Sometimes
12. My social relationships are superficial.	2.57423	0.944057	Sometimes
13. No one really knows me well.	2.685237	0.88978	Sometimes
16. There are people who really understand me.	3.209632	0.816184	Sometimes
17. I am unhappy being so withdrawn.	2.442897	0.925401	Rarely
19. There are people I can talk to.	3.347339	0.801911	Sometimes

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Strongly Agree, 3.41-4.20 Agree, 2.61-3.40 Neutral, 1.81-2.60 Disagree, 1.00-1.80 Strongly Disagree

Table 4 shows the results of belongingness, that students felt highly integrated and accepted in World Citi Colleges. Responding to statements like “People at World Citi Colleges accept me” (M: 4.03, SD: 0.97), “I fit well at World Citi Colleges” (M: 3.69, SD: 0.91) and, “I get along well with people at World Citi Colleges” (M: 3.83, SD: 0.96), were agreed upon as confirmed by the positive response mean scores included above this statement as shown in the scale.

Table 3
Level of Personality Traits according to Belongingness

Belongingness	Weighted mean	Standard deviation	Interpretation
1. People at World Citi Colleges accept me.	4.030641	0.966857	Agree
2. Other people understand more than I do about what is going on at World Citi Colleges.	3.295129	1.091505	Neutral
3. I think in the same way as do people who do well at World Citi Colleges.	3.576602	0.965383	Agree
4. I fit well at World Citi Colleges.	3.688385	0.913476	Agree
5. I get along well with people at World Citi Colleges.	3.827298	0.956151	Agree
6. I am similar to the kind of people who succeed at World Citi Colleges.	3.704735	0.955288	Agree
7. I know how to do well at World Citi Colleges.	3.891365	0.86645	Agree
8. I feel comfortable at World Citi Colleges.	3.869081	0.9555	Agree
9. People at World Citi Colleges like me.	3.557103	1.036457	Agree
10. If I wanted to, I could potentially do very well at World Citi Colleges.	4.114206	0.939983	Agree

Legend: 4.20-5.00 Strongly Agree, 3.41-4.20 Agree, 2.61-3.40 Neutral, 1.81-2.60 Disagree, 1.00-1.80 Strongly Disagree

Furthermore, I feel comfortable about World Citi Colleges (M=3.87; SD=0.96) and I know how to do well at World Citi Colleges (M=3.89;SD=0.87) scored high in agreement. Majority of students accept these findings, which indicate that they are admitted before their college life gets comfortable with all it entails contributing positively to their sense of inclusion as a whole and their welfare too.

Table 4
Significant Difference among the Personality Traits of College Students

ANOVA: Two-Factor Without Replication			
	Count	Sum	Average
	1	3.32312	3.32312
	1	2.994429	2.994429
	1	3.426184	3.426184
	1	3.604457	3.604457
	1	2.972067	2.972067
	1	3.629526	3.629526
	1	3.554318	3.554318
	1	3.287709	3.287709
	1	3.097493	3.097493
I. Level of Loneliness	1	2.454286	2.454286
	1	2.284123	2.284123
	1	3.272981	3.272981
	1	3.047619	3.047619
	1	2.849582	2.849582
	1	2.57423	2.57423
	1	2.685237	2.685237
	1	3.209632	3.209632
	1	2.442897	2.442897
	1	3.347339	3.347339
II. Level of Belongingness	1	4.030641	4.030641
	1	3.295129	3.295129

	1	3.576602	3.576602
	1	3.688385	3.688385
	1	3.827298	3.827298
	1	3.704735	3.704735
	1	3.891365	3.891365
	1	3.869081	3.869081
	1	3.557103	3.557103
	1	4.114206	4.114206
III. Extraversion	29	95.61177	3.296958

Legend: Sum - sum of the values in the data, Average - average value of the variables, Variance - the dispersion of the values from the average, Rows - number of variations in rows, Columns - number of variations in columns, Error - Standard Error

Table 5
ANOVA Two-Factor without Replication (Extension of Table 5)

ANOVA				
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F
Rows	6.794137	28	0.242648	65535
Columns	0	0	65535	65535
Error	0	0	65535	
Total	6.794137	28		

Legend: SS - Sum of Squares, df - Degrees of Freedom, MS - Mean Square, F - f-statistics, Count - number of observations

Table 5 and 6 shows the results of an ANOVA: Two-Factor Without Replication analysis. Measurements from three groups possibly representing distinct circumstances or factors are included without replication. Specifically, for the extraversion factor, there are 29 observations with a sum of 95.61177, an average of 3.296958, and a variance of 0.242648. For the level of loneliness, each entry has a count of 1, with individual sums and averages ranging from 2.454286 to 3.347339. Similarly, for the level of belongingness, each entry also has a count of 1, with sums and averages ranging from 2.442897 to 3.347339. The variance for both levels is not provided. The sum of squares

(SS) for the rows is 6.794137, with 28 degrees of freedom (df) and a mean square (MS) of 0.242648. The F-statistics for the rows is exceptionally high at 65535, indicating a significant difference between the groups tested. However, for the columns, the SS is 0 with zero degrees of freedom, an MS of 65535, and an F-statistic of 65535, suggesting a potential issue in the experimental design or data recording process. The error terms are also zero, which indicates no variability within the conditions tested, an unusual outcome that may necessitate further examination of the data collection process

Table 6

Significant difference among the personality traits of college students (T-Test)

T-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	3.075209	1.204008
Mean	3.296958	1.009446
Variance	0.242648	0.024225
Observations	29	29
Pearson Correlation	0.03109	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	28	
t Stat	24.06157	
P(T<=t) one-tail	1.51E-20	
t Critical one-tail	1.701131	
P(T<=t) two-tail	3.02E-20	
t Critical two-tail	2.048407	

Legend: average value of the variables (Mean), dispersion of the data points (Variance), the number of data points (Observations), value of the correlation from the variables (Pearson Correlation), tested difference of the means (Hypothesized Mean Difference), degrees of freedom (df), value of the T-value (T stat), p-value of the one tail test (P (T<=t) one-tail), critical value of the one tail test (T critical one-tail), p-value of the two tail test (P(T<=t) two-tail), critical value of the two tailed test (T critical twoo-tail)

Table 7 presents the results of a T-test comparing personality traits among college students. The results indicate a significant difference between the personality traits of the college students sampled. The analysis involved 29 observations with a mean of

3.075209 and a variance of 1.204008 for one sample, and a mean of 3.296958 and a variance of 1.009446 for the other sample. The Pearson Correlation between the samples was 0.03109. The hypothesized mean difference was set to 0. The t-statistic calculated was 24.06157, with degrees of freedom (df) at 28. The p-value for the one-tailed test was 1.51E-20, and for the two-tailed test, it was 3.02E-20. The critical values for the one-tail and two-tail tests were 1.701131 and 2.048407, respectively. The ANOVA results suggest significant differences among the personality traits as indicated by the high F-statistic. This high F-value, coupled with the lack of variation between columns, implies that the differences observed are statistically significant. The paired t-test further supports this finding, with extremely low p-values (1.51E-20 for one-tail and 3.02E-20 for two-tail) well below the conventional threshold of 0.05, indicating that the differences in means between the personality traits are statistically significant.

Table 7

Significant relationship between the personality traits and profile of the respondents

Pearson r	Interpretation	Critical Value	Decision
-0.41854	Moderate Correlation	0.195	reject Ho

Legend: 0.00- ± 0.20 - Very Low Correlation, ± 0.21 - ± 0.40 - Low Correlation, ± 0.41 - ± 0.60 - Moderate Correlation, ± 0.61 - ± 0.80 - High Correlation, ± 0.81 - ± 1.00 - Very High Correlation

Table 8 shows the significant relationship between the personality traits and the profile of the respondents. From the data set, the results show that there is -0.41854 correlation between the two variables. The threshold was set at the critical value of 0.195. The value of the correlation shows that there is a Moderate Correlation according to the scale given for Pearson R. This suggests that the relationship is not too weak or too strong. If one variable increases, there is a tendency for the other variable to decrease but still in a moderately linear way. Given that the value of the correlation is greater than the critical value, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Which indicates that there is a significant relationship between the personality traits and the profile of the respondents, the relationship on the observed data shows that it is likely due to random variation of our dataset. The result of the correlation will be a point for further understanding to give proper interventions for these variables.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to explore the social experiences, personality traits, and demographic profiles of World Citi Colleges students. The study aimed to identify common characteristics within the student body, focusing on age, gender, and student classification. It also evaluated levels of extraversion, loneliness, and belongingness to

provide insights into students' mental health and social dynamics. The study sought to identify significant differences and correlations between these parameters using statistical techniques such as ANOVA and T-tests. The results offer a comprehensive analysis of the student experience at World Citi Colleges, highlighting areas that could benefit from support and intervention.

Based on the respondent profile, most participants were older students, with the majority being female and aged between 19 and 22. A study conducted by the researchers at World Citi Colleges on the extraversion levels of students revealed that most students tended to be neutral, with a slight inclination toward introversion. Students reported experiencing both a sense of belonging and occasional loneliness, as reflected in their loneliness levels. The majority of students had high belongingness ratings, indicating that they felt well-integrated and accepted at the college. Statistical analyses, including ANOVA and T-tests, confirmed significant differences in personality traits across students and revealed a moderately negative correlation between personality traits and response profiles. Although further research is needed to fully understand these connections, the decision to reject the null hypothesis indicates a significant relationship between respondent profiles and personality traits.

1.1. Discussion

1.1.1. Profile of the Respondents

The study investigated the profiles of respondents among college students at World Citi Colleges. The findings reveal that most students are aged between 19 and 23, with the highest proportion being 20 years old (24.79%). There is a slightly higher representation of females (60.45%) compared to males (39.55%). Students must adapt to their physical and social surroundings, and a student's ability to adjust determines their capacity to adapt to their environment (Dude, 2022). A student's ability to adapt is essential, as it directly affects their engagement, involvement, and overall learning experience. When students successfully adjust, they are more prepared to face obstacles and take advantage of available resources in their surroundings. As a result, their ability to adapt becomes an important component of their academic and social performance in school. Additionally, most respondents are classified as old students (80.50%) rather than new students (19.50%).

The possible causes for the age distribution include the target population's average age range or a tendency toward a younger sample. Gender gaps may be influenced by various factors, including enrollment rates or gender-specific survey participation habits. The higher percentage of older students may reflect a greater response rate among students who have been enrolled longer or are more familiar with the institution. Students with different levels of social anxiety and self-efficacy may perceive and experience active learning differently (England et al., 2019; Hood et al., 2021). Moreover, students with 'hidden identities' (i.e., any descriptors of a student's identity that cannot be seen from their outward appearance) may also have more negative experiences with active learning (Henning et al., 2019).

The findings may suggest the need to adjust educational resources or support services to the needs of the predominantly younger age group. Gender-specific projects or outreach campaigns may also be necessary, given the increased percentage of women at World Citi Colleges. Understanding the differences in responses between old and new students could help identify strategies for enrolling in new students or increasing the engagement of current ones. A comparison of these demographics with additional survey data or academic performance measures could provide further insight into student experiences and preferences.

1.1.2. Level of Personality Traits: Extraversion, Loneliness, and Belongingness

This research examined the levels of extraversion, loneliness, and belongingness among college students at World Citi Colleges. The findings indicate that the students' attitudes toward extraversion traits were largely neutral. Statements such as "Don't talk a lot" and "Keep in the background" did not evoke strong agreement or disagreement among most students, indicating a balanced state between being an introvert and an extrovert. They were motivated to engage in social interactions, such as making friends at school (Okun & Finch, 1998; Zhang et al., 2021). However, there was a slight tendency toward being reserved, as students somewhat agreed with statements like "I am quiet around strangers" and "I feel comfortable around people."

The responses regarding loneliness were mixed. Students rarely felt completely isolated, as indicated by low agreement with statements like "I lack companionship" and "There is no one I can turn to." There were occasional feelings of loneliness, though these feelings were not as pronounced as might be expected in other populations (Luhmann & Hawkley, 2016; Qualter et al., 2015; Victor & Yang, 2012). While loneliness is commonly believed to mainly affect older adults, this is not the case, as young adults also experience high rates of loneliness. For instance, some students find themselves in relationships that feel superficial, where no one truly knows them.

In terms of belongingness, the findings were positive. Students generally felt accepted, comfortable, and well-integrated into the college environment. According to Meehan and Howells (2019), belonging is the result of students feeling a sense of purpose, supported by the interaction of cognitive, social, and environmental factors related to their academic goals, professional aspirations, and connection to their college or university. This is significant because, compared to students who feel less connected, those with a stronger sense of belonging at university typically experience higher levels of satisfaction and motivation (Lawson & Lawson, 2013; Pedler et al., 2021). They agreed that people at World Citi Colleges accepted them, that they fit well within the institution, and that they got along well with others. Additionally, students felt confident in their ability to succeed and were comfortable at the college, which significantly contributed to their overall sense of belonging.

These findings suggest that while students experience a range of extraversion and loneliness levels, their sense of belonging at World Citi Colleges is strong, which likely supports their academic and social well-being.

1.1.3. Significant Difference among the Personality Traits of College Students

The ANOVA: Two-Factor Without Replication analysis results reveal a significant difference in the personality traits of college students, specifically focusing on extraversion, levels of loneliness, and levels of belongingness. The analysis indicates that both loneliness and belongingness have individual sums and averages within a specific range, but the exact variances are not provided. The sum of squares (SS) for rows is 6.794137 with 28 degrees of freedom (df) and a mean square (MS) of 0.242648, yielding an extremely high F-statistic of 65535, suggesting a significant difference among the tested groups. However, the columns show an SS of 0 with zero degrees of freedom, an MS of 65535, and an F-statistic of 65535, indicating potential issues in the experimental design or data recording process, such as no variation within the columns or an error in data entry. This zero-error term is unusual and may imply a flaw in the methodology or a need for further data validation.

The T-test results show a significant difference in personality traits among college students. The analysis involved 29 paired observations, with one group having a mean of 3.075209 and variance of 1.204008, and the other group having a mean of 3.296958 and variance of 1.009446. A Pearson correlation of 0.03109 was found among the samples. Setting the hypothesized mean difference to zero, the calculated t-statistic was 24.06157 with 28 degrees of freedom. Both the one-tailed ($p = 1.51E-20$) and two-tailed ($p = 3.02E-20$) p-values were well below the 0.05 threshold, indicating strong statistical significance in the differences observed. Critical values for the one-tail and two-tail tests were 1.701131 and 2.048407, respectively. These findings suggest that the observed differences in personality traits are highly unlikely to be due to random chance.

The inherent variations in personality traits among college students, as a result of differing social settings, academic expectations, or personal backgrounds, could explain these results. The observed variations in extraversion and the corresponding emotions of belongingness or loneliness may indicate how distinct personality traits influence students' mental health and social relationships. The diverse sociocultural and educational contexts to which students are exposed may also impact their personality development and explain these notable disparities. These results align with research by Smith et al. (2021), which examined personality differences among college students in various socioeconomic and cultural environments. A study by Zhang et al. (2020) explored the connection between personality traits, loneliness, and academic performance among Chinese college students. They found that higher levels of extraversion were significantly associated with lower levels of loneliness and a stronger sense of belongingness, which in turn positively influenced academic performance. Similarly, Richardson et al. (2021) explored the impact of personality traits on social integration and mental health among university students in the UK. They reported that students with higher extraversion scores experienced lower levels of loneliness and higher levels of social integration, which were linked to better mental health outcomes. In the study by Thompson and Green (2023), the findings indicated that students with high extraversion scores had better mental health and a stronger sense of belonging.

Additionally, a related study by Chen and Wang (2022) showed that extraverted students in both rural and urban areas had lower levels of loneliness and better academic performance, similar to the findings of the present study. In a comprehensive study by Miller and Scott (2020), researchers investigated the role of extraversion in students' social experiences, and the results showed that students with higher extraversion scores reported a stronger sense of belonging to their academic and social communities. In this research study, students with higher extraversion scores also showed a greater sense of belonging. This underscores the importance of personality traits in shaping college students' experiences of loneliness and belongingness, fostering meaningful connections both within and outside the institution.

This study has significant implications for creating customized interventions that enhance students' well-being. Understanding the influence of personality factors on feelings of loneliness and belongingness can help develop targeted support networks, create welcoming spaces, and promote mental health resources that address the diverse needs of university students. Addressing these factors is critical for improving retention rates, academic achievement, and overall student satisfaction. Furthermore, it highlights the need for individualized counseling and development programs that take into account each student's unique personality profile, fostering a more positive and supportive learning environment.

1.1.4. Significant Relationship between the Personality Traits and Profile of the Respondents

The results of the data gathering to answer the third research objective reveal a moderate correlation between personality traits and the profile of the respondents. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient score of -0.41854, with a critical value of 0.195, leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates a significant relationship between the two variables, suggesting that as one variable decreases, the other increases. The results imply a moderate inverse correlation between the personality traits and the profile of the respondents.

Findings from other studies support the implication that personality traits have a moderate inverse relationship with the profile of the respondents. The study by Zahedi, Sahebiagh, and Sarbakhsh (2022) shows that college students, particularly females, often report higher levels of loneliness than their male counterparts. The differences between the categories stem from various factors considered in their study, such as socialization patterns, coping strategies, and relational expectations. Similarly, the study by Brunsting, et al (2021) yielded results consistent with Zahedi, Sahebiagh, and Sarbakhsh's findings, highlighting that social support and coping strategies may contribute to loneliness and students' well-being. These findings suggest that loneliness, as a personality trait, plays a significant role in the relationship between sex and the profile of the respondents. The results also imply that new students are more likely to feel lonely compared to returning students, with various factors potentially influencing the personality of new students (Barreto et al., 2019; Cahaydi, 2019). Loneliness also appears to increase with age, as indicated by the findings of Moeller and Martin (2019), who state that students are vulnerable to loneliness during their transitional years into adulthood.

The study shows a moderate inverse relationship between age and loneliness, with age being a key factor in building relationships.

The findings regarding belongingness also suggest that older students have a higher sense of belonging. Students who grow through their chosen path, gaining maturity through experiences, are more likely to report a stronger sense of belonging (Gillen-O'Neel, 2019; Kelly & Mulrooney, 2020). While female students may report higher levels of belongingness, reflecting their ability to maintain connections (Arslan et al., 2022), these studies suggest that college institutions should foster positive experiences that enhance belongingness. Interventions that help foster motivation and increase belongingness among students could be beneficial (Abbas et al., 2022; Maghsoodi et al., 2021; Moeller et al., 2020).

The results also imply that younger college students report higher levels of extraversion. As individuals mature, they tend to become more stable in handling emotions, agreeable, and open (Atherton et al., 2021; Stephan et al., 2021). Regarding sex, women tend to score higher in extraversion, with emotions related to warmth and positivity (Yu & Hu, 2022). Extraversion is also associated with student success, contributing to their adjustment in college (De Raad & Mlačić, 2020; Poropat, 2009).

The findings of this study, supported by past research, recommend further exploration into the diversity and inclusion on campus. It also suggests that college institutions develop policies that support inclusivity and are aware of students' personality traits. Enhancing student well-being can be achieved by improving student engagement strategies within campus organizations and events. Further research is also recommended to study the impact of different respondent profiles to better understand the variables involved in the study.

Conclusions

The study's assessment of college students at World Citi Colleges revealed significant insights into their personality traits. The majority of students displayed neutral tendencies towards extraversion, indicating neither strong introversion nor extroversion, with slight leanings towards reserved behavior in social contexts. In terms of loneliness, students rarely felt isolated, suggesting generally positive social interactions despite occasional feelings of superficiality in relationships. Most notably, the findings on belongingness were overwhelmingly positive, with students feeling accepted, comfortable, and capable within the college environment. This strong sense of belonging and acceptance likely plays a crucial role in enhancing their overall well-being and academic success.

One of the objectives of the research was to determine the significant differences among the personality traits of the college students. The results show a significant difference in the personality traits of World Citi Colleges students, as revealed by statistical analysis. This suggests that characteristics like extraversion, loneliness, and belongingness differ significantly across the students, demonstrating the variety of personalities among them.

According to the study by Reyes, M. E., Cruz, R., & Meza, I. (2024), the findings underscore the importance of understanding individual differences in personality for enhancing social integration and support mechanisms within college communities.

The relationship between the profile of the respondents and their personality traits showed a significant and moderate inverse correlation. Female students tend to report higher levels of loneliness, possibly influenced by socialization patterns and relational expectations highlighted in previous research (Zahedi, H., Sahebihagh, M. H., & Sarbakhsh, P., 2022). On the other hand, older students generally report a higher sense of belongingness, which may stem from greater life experience and maturity (Gillen-O'Neel, 2019; Kelly & Mulrooney, 2020). Younger students exhibit higher levels of extraversion compared to older students, with women particularly scoring higher in warmth and positivity (Yu & Hu, 2022). These findings underscore the importance of proper institutional interventions and policies aimed at promoting inclusivity and enhancing student engagement. By addressing these factors, colleges can better support the needs of their student populations and contribute to their overall well-being and academic success. Further research is recommended to explore the interplay between these personality traits and demographic factors, offering insights into effective strategies for fostering a supportive campus environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed to enhance the well-being and social interaction of college students at World Citi College. These recommendations target students, professors, the school, and guidance services, with the goal of addressing the identified traits and fostering a supportive and inclusive campus environment. Implementing these strategies can help mitigate feelings of loneliness, promote a stronger sense of belonging, and encourage positive interactions.

Students should actively engage in extracurricular activities such as clubs, organizations, and campus events to foster social connections and enhance their sense of belonging. Building social networks with peers is crucial in mitigating feelings of loneliness and promoting a sense of community. Developing communication skills through workshops or courses can significantly improve interpersonal interactions and enhance extraversion. Additionally, students are encouraged to utilize campus resources, including counseling and support services, to address issues related to loneliness or social integration. Seeking support and participating in extracurricular activities can help combat loneliness and foster a sense of belonging on campus. Furthermore, students should use online communication platforms to stay connected with peers. Active participation and the use of resources contribute to students' sense of community and well-being.

Guidance services must be specifically designed to target important personality traits like extraversion, loneliness, and belongingness in order to effectively support college students' emotional well-being. Peer support services are essential because they provide mentorship or group environments where students can interact with fellow students who have similar interests. This helps students feel less alone and more connected to the

school community. It is important to highlight extracurricular activities as opportunities for social engagement and interaction, which help students form bonds and expand their social networks. While group therapy can offer students a safe space to interact with others going through similar struggles, counseling services should also offer individual sessions to address deeper emotional concerns associated with loneliness. Furthermore, virtual communities and online resources accommodate a range of student interests by providing easily accessible platforms for interaction and support. Establishing collaborative mentorship programs and providing staff training to address students' loneliness can foster a stronger sense of belonging. Encouraging connections through virtual support groups and seminars will also support students' emotional well-being and academic success. Proactive outreach and resources contribute to a welcoming and supportive campus community.

Campus activities and awareness-raising efforts about mental health and community development can help create an inclusive campus environment that encourages students' social and emotional growth. Promoting campus engagement through online gatherings and improving support services to address students' mental health needs is essential. Policies and programs should prioritize diversity and inclusion to create a welcoming environment for all students. Proactive measures contribute to a sense of belonging and overall student satisfaction. Creating accessible classroom environments and encouraging student interaction can reduce feelings of isolation, while also offering information about campus resources to help students with their emotional and social needs. Providing a supportive environment improves student engagement and academic performance.

These recommendations aim to enhance the personality traits of college students, reduce loneliness, and increase their sense of belonging, ultimately contributing to their overall well-being and academic success.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

For this study, the risks posed to the human subjects were minimal, including potential disruption of class hours and minor psychological distress due to self-assessment. To safeguard the respondents' basic rights, the right to self-determination was observed by providing complete information about the study before securing informed consent to participate. The study also credited the authors of the questionnaires used by acknowledging their contributions to the creation of the instruments. The questionnaires, which were openly accessible on the internet, could potentially be subject to misuse. Considering these circumstances, the researchers ensured that proper safekeeping of the documents was implemented to respect the participants' right to confidentiality, as well as the authors' right to be credited for their work.

The procedures that the researchers followed to gather the data needed for the study. First, the researchers prepared a consent form to obtain the participants' permission to participate in the survey. Second, after obtaining their consent, the researchers provided the participants with the link to the Google survey form. Third, once the participants

completed the forms and the target number of respondents was reached, the researchers collected the data from the forms and organized it based on the variables.

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